

QUIZ**LAST NAME: ZRAIBI****FIRST NAME: COLETTE****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes).
The author did use Zotero to insert references.
The author did not use Grammarly Premium.
The author used the following software: MSWord 2008 on Windows 10.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Writing a research dissertation

- is a rigorous work that requires a lot of thinking, preparation and planning.¹
- does not require to follow a style for writing.
- follows a process from the start of the research to its completion.²
- requires the guidance and the direction from an advisor.³

2. To complete a sound and credible research dissertation, the research student shall

- focus on a sound and doable topic, that is clear and concise.⁴

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 2.

² Ibid., 179.

³ Ibid., 17.

⁴ Ibid., 6.

- consistently apply a selected style and format.⁵
- cite all and any sources of information that he uses.⁶
- rely on his intuition and feelings as evidence to reach good conclusions.

3. The Turabian style

- is the Chicago style applied to research papers.⁷
- can only be used when you cite from books and journal articles.
- covers two Chicago styles of source citation – the notes-bibliography format and the author-date format.⁸
- can automatically be generated for citations when using citation management software, like Zotero.⁹

4. In the notes-bibliography style of the Turabian style,

- the information source is cited either in a footnote or in an endnote. Additionally, there is a bibliography list of references at the end of the paper.¹⁰
- bibliography is located at the end of the paper and shall list all sources the author read.
- the parenthetical citation includes the author, the date, the title, and the relevant page numbers.

⁵ Ibid., 23.

⁶ Ibid., 24.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 44.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition., Chicago guides to writing, editing, and publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 11.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck, *ACA-401D Period 2 – EUCLID University LMS*, n.d., accessed September 27, 2020, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-2/>.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 87.

- the reference list is arranged chronologically according to the year of publication, and then alphabetically by the last name of the author.
5. **If a research student wants to identify and develop a researchable topic, what should he do?¹¹**
- Select a topic, that he can focus on.**
 - Begin to examine and become familiar with the available literature related to the topic.**
 - Begin sharpening the topical focus and narrow the topic.**
 - Refine the problem to be addressed and think whether the problem can and should be researched in the first place.**
6. **What are the next steps involved in the research process?**
- Lay out and articulate the problem statement, through developing a research purpose and associated research questions.¹²**
 - Collect, analyze, and synthesize the data.¹³**
 - Ask the advisor to present the conclusions and recommendations.
 - Present and publish the research.¹⁴**
7. **The qualitative research approach...**
- is selected based on the nature of the research problem.¹⁵**
 - includes five primary approaches in designing a qualitative study.¹⁶**

¹¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 5–7.

¹² *Ibid.*, xxi.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, 176.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 25.

¹⁶ Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*, 2016, accessed December 8, 2020, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&feature=emb_logo.

- shall be presented in the methodology chapter to indicate the appropriateness of the various design features of the student's research.¹⁷
- is the same as the quantitative research approach.
8. **The literature review...**
- should be well organized and shall include only relevant information directly related to the research problem and the purpose of the study.¹⁸
- involves only books and journal articles.
- consists in summarizing what the student read.
- consists in identifying and locating what is already known about the problem and what lacks and needs further research.¹⁹
9. **What is the purpose of writing the Methodology chapter?²⁰**
- It tells readers about the decisions and actions taken in the research study.
- It tells why the research student took these decisions.
- It tells how the research student implemented these decisions.
- All of these.
10. **What are the other challenges after data collection?**
- . Reduce raw data into research findings.²¹

¹⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 48.

¹⁸ Ibid., 18–19.

¹⁹ Ibid., 49.

²⁰ Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*.

²¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 96.

- Find the appropriate data processor to analyze the data.
- Develop an understanding of what these findings really mean.**²²
- Determine how useful the findings are in illuminating the research questions being explored.**²³

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²² Ibid., 127.

²³ Ibid., 131.